

SIMULATION OF THE SEVERE PLASTIC DEFORMATION OF AISI 1045 CARBON STEEL DURING EQUAL CHANNEL ANGULAR PRESSING (ECAP)

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ABSTRACT: Equal Channel Angular Pressing (ECAP) is a high-strain plastic deformation process used to enhance the mechanical properties of materials, particularly metals, by subjecting them to severe deformation. This process is widely employed to refine the microstructure of materials, thereby improving their performance. The objective of this study is to investigate the influence of two critical process parameters the channel angle (Φ) and the friction coefficient (μ) between the workpiece and the die channel on the distribution of plastic deformations and deformation inhomogeneity during a single pass of ECAP. This investigation is conducted using the Finite Element simulation program ABAQUS. A 3D finite element model incorporating varying channel angles (Φ) and friction coefficients (μ) is developed for this purpose. For each case study, the distribution and inhomogeneity of the equivalent plastic deformation (PEEQ), as well as its evolution over time, are analyzed. The results demonstrate that plastic deformations increase as the channel angle decreases and the friction coefficient increases. Additionally, the findings reveal that deformation inhomogeneity can be minimized by carefully selecting optimal process parameters. The results exhibit a high degree of consistency with those reported in the literature, confirming that the proposed 3D finite element model accurately simulates the distribution of plastic deformations during the ECAP process.

KEYWORDS: Abaqus CAE; FEM; Inhomogeneity; Steel; Severe Plastic Deformation

1 INTRODUCTION

Severe plastic deformations (SPD) represent promising processes for refining the microstructure of materials and improving their mechanical properties. Among the SPD techniques is the equal channel angular pressing (ECAP), which is of particular interest as it allows for high plastic deformation without altering the dimensions of the sample. Repeating the ECAP process several times can achieve exceptionally high deformation and significant microstructural refinement. The reduction in grain size leads to a notable increase in yield strength, tensile strength, and hardness. However, further developments are necessary to maintain sufficient ductility. Manipulating the microstructure at the nanometric scale through these intensive mechanical processes significantly optimizes the mechanical performance of materials [1].

The finite element method (FEM) has been used to examine the impact of various factors, such as material properties, the corner angle of ECAP dies, and the friction between the billet and dies, on the

deformation distribution within the billet [2]. Numerous researchers have investigated the microstructure and mechanical properties of ultrafine-grained low-carbon steel [3-4], copper [5], titanium and titanium alloys [6-9], aluminum alloys [10-11], and magnesium alloys [12] produced through ECAP.

Several factors influence the workability and microstructural characteristics of the pressed billets when materials are processed using ECAP. These include the channel angle (Φ) of the die [13-14] and the outer curvature arc (Ψ) where the channels intersect [15].

According to Valiev et al. [16-17], the pressing speeds often range between 1 and 20 mm/s. The ultimate size of the ultrafine grains is not significantly affected by them. However, microstructures, appear to be more stable at lower pressing speeds. The temperature during the pressing process affects the microstructure. Low temperature preferably room temperature, is optimal for efficient

grain refining. The presence of a lack of back pressure should also be considered.

The number of passes in the ECAP process has a significant impact on the properties of materials. Segal et al. [18] emphasized the significance of rotation between numerous passes, noting that differing pathways between passes would result in distinct microstructures.

Steels generally exhibit low strength in the coarse-grained state. Equal channel angular pressing (ECAP) is a feasible method to significantly enhance the strength of materials through grain refinement via severe plastic deformation (SPD). Muñoz et al. [19] studied the microstructural evolution, plastic anisotropy, and mechanical behavior of duplex stainless steel (DSS) processed by the ECAP technique. The ECAP treatment achieved a yield strength exceeding 1.1 GPa after a single ECAP pass. It was shown that austenite is the phase that provides more hardening, while ferrite ensures ductility.

Huang et al. [20] examined how temperature affected the microstructures and tensile properties of 304L austenitic stainless steel processed by equal channel angular pressing (ECAP) within the temperature range of 500 to 900°C. They discovered that the best combination of high yield strength and significant elongation to fracture occurs at 800°C (605 MPa and 37%).

Zheng et al. [21] investigated the annealing temperature of a 304 austenitic stainless steel (ASS) subjected to equal channel angular pressing (ECAP) to customize the bimodal microstructure and achieve the optimized combination of high strength and high ductility. The coarse-grained ASS is first refined to a nanograined (NG) level by ECAP over eight passes. The NG microstructure with high dislocation density offers higher strength but lower ductility. The ductility of ultrafine-grained (UFG) or NG materials produced by SPD can be restored through appropriate post-SPD annealing without significant loss of strength.

Vincentis et al. [22] evaluated the microstructure anisotropy of a low-content F138 steel deformed by

equal channel angular pressing (ECAP) up to four passes at room temperature (RT) and at 300°C. The microstructure developed during severe plastic deformation leads to an improvement in mechanical properties due to the reduction in grain size and the accumulation of defects, mainly dislocation networks. The objective of this study is to investigate the influence of the variation in the channel angle and friction coefficient of steel on the distribution and inhomogeneity of plastic deformation (PEEQ) for a single pass during the ECAP process and also to optimize the process parameters using the finite element method (FEM) via the Abaqus software. The paper is structured as follows: Section two details the experimental procedure, including the chemical composition of AISI 1045 steel and the tensile test. Section three presents the numerical simulation of the Equal Channel Angular Pressing (ECAP) process. Section four provides the validation of the studied model. The paper concludes with a summary of the findings and concluding remarks.

2 MATERIAL

In the mechanical industry, steel is finding numerous applications due to its promising properties such as strength, durability, workability, and versatility. Additionally, mechanical industries use structural steels because of their ability to straightforwardly accept heat treatments for strength enhancement.

AISI 1045 steel, selected for this study, is a medium carbon steel designed for service in areas requiring greater strength and higher toughness. Its chemical composition is given in Table 1.

The numerical modeling of ECAP requires determination of the material's mechanical characteristics in both the elastic region and under large plastic deformations (deformations from 100% to 400%). The stress-strain curve was observed up to 400%, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Table 1. Chemical composition of AISI 1045 steel.

% C	% Si	% Mn	% P	% S	% Cr	% Ni	% Al
0.42-0.50	0.35	0.8	0.04	0.045	0.40	0.40	0.02

Figure 1. Stress-strain curve of the billet material.

3 NUMERICAL SIMULATION

To simulate the ECAP technique, we utilized the model illustrated in Figure 2. This model includes a cylindrical workpiece with a 10 mm diameter and 50 mm length, a punch with a 10 mm diameter and 10 mm length, and a Die with dimensions

100×100×130. The ECAP matrices have a prismatic shape, with channel angles of $\Phi=90^\circ, 100^\circ, 110^\circ, 120^\circ, 130^\circ$ and an outer corner angle $\psi=10^\circ$. The entry and exit channels match the workpiece diameter.

Figure 2. 3D FEM model (a) Workpiece (b) Punch (c) Die (d) 1/2 model (e) 3D model.

The objective of this study is to analyze the equivalent plastic strains (PEEQ) in steel subjected to severe deformation using the ECAP technique. This involves examining two process parameters: the matrix channel angle (Φ) and the friction coefficient (μ) between the workpiece and the matrix channel.

To study the influence of the channel angle, we considered and modeled the matrix with channel angles of $\Phi=90^\circ$, 100° , 110° , 120° , and 130° , an outer corner angle of $\psi=10^\circ$, and a friction coefficient (μ) of 0.08, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Modeling of matrices with different channel angles $\Phi=90^\circ$, 100° , 110° , 120° , and 130° .

To study the influence of the friction coefficient between the workpiece and the matrix channel, we considered a matrix with a channel angle of $\Phi=90^\circ$, an outer corner angle of $\psi=10^\circ$, and friction

coefficients (μ) of 0, 0.0001, and 0.08. The modeling and simulation were performed using the finite element method with ABAQUS software.

Figure 4. Meshing of different components (a) Matrix (b) Punch (c) workpiece (d) Overall meshing (e) Boundary and loading conditions.

Given the symmetry of the model relative to the median plane of the ECAP matrix, symmetrical boundary conditions are applied to half of the workpiece, punch, and matrix, as illustrated in Figure 4(e). The workpiece is considered as an elastic-plastic material, featuring a Young's modulus of 210 GPa, a Poisson's ratio of 0.3, and a yield strength of 110 GPa. The simulation was conducted at room temperature, with the workpiece pressed in a single

pass without rotation. In the simulation, the matrix and punch were modeled as rigid bodies, while the workpiece was considered a deformable body. A displacement of 50 mm was applied to the punch in the extrusion direction. The ABAQUS software is used for the determination of the equivalent plastic strains distribution in the contact zone. The mesh of the workpiece is conducted with C3D8R element with reduced integration and hourglass control. It is

an 8-node linear brick element, meaning it has 8 nodes. The C3D8R element is commonly used in simulations involving large deformations, nonlinear materials, and contact problems. This simulation has led to 2838 elements for workpiece mesh.

4 FINITE ELEMENT RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Influence of the Channel Angle Φ :

To investigate the effect of the channel angle Φ , a finite element analysis was performed to determine

the distribution and inhomogeneity of the equivalent plastic strains (PEEQ), as well as the evolution of PEEQ in an element of the billet along the channel during a single pass using ABAQUS. The distributions of equivalent plastic strains for different channel angles are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Distribution of equivalent plastic strain (PEEQ) in the 5 cases: (a) $\Phi = 90^\circ$, (b) $\Phi = 100^\circ$, (c) $\Phi = 110^\circ$, (d) $\Phi = 120^\circ$, (e) $\Phi = 130^\circ$.

The five models are represented with five different channel angles: 90° , 100° , 110° , 120° , and 130° . It is observed that the smallest angle results in

higher deformation levels. The comparison between these cases focuses on how the increase in the channel angle influences the localization and

intensity of plastic strain within the material. In the central region, the equivalent plastic strains are significantly more uniform and pronounced compared to those in the lower and upper regions of the workpiece. The uniformity of strain plays a critical role in interpreting the results of these simulations. It is essential to evaluate whether the strain is distributed evenly throughout the material or if there are areas of particularly high or low concentration. This strain homogeneity provides valuable insights into the quality of the deformation process and the material's response to the imposed conditions. The homogeneity of strain is influenced by the number of passes. As the number of passes increases, the degree of homogeneity also increases. In this study, the number of passes is set to 1. These results indicate that the channel angle has a significant effect on the consistency of deformation. An increase in the angle appears to result in more uneven deformation. This variability could influence the ultimate mechanical properties of the AISI 1045 steel, which may vary from one region to another within the workpiece.

4.2 Evolution of Equivalent Plastic Strain:

The analysis of the evolution of plastic strain throughout the process is of critical importance for evaluating the response of our steel to severe plastic deformation. We examined how the channel angle affects the evolution of plastic strain during the process by studying five different angles: 90°, 100°, 110°, 120°, and 130°. To track the evolution of strain during our process, a specific mesh element of the workpiece was selected for continuous monitoring throughout the simulation.

Figure 6. Diagram of the evolution of PEEQ during the ECAP process for the 5 cases.

For an angle of 130 degrees, the strain starts at 0 and gradually increases to reach a value of 0.423. For

an angle of 120 degrees, the strain also starts at 0 but increases rapidly to reach a value of 0.576. For an angle of 110 degrees, the strain also starts at 0 but increases quickly to reach a value of 0.972. For an angle of 100 degrees, the strain also starts at 0 but rises rapidly to reach a value of 1.307. For an angle of 90 degrees, the strain starts at 0 and increases more moderately to reach a value of 1.557 at a time of 0.5 seconds.

Figure 6 clearly demonstrates that the evolution of equivalent plastic strain (PEEQ) over time is significantly influenced by the channel angle in the ECAP process. For the five channel angles analyzed, the strain increases progressively over time, but the rate of increase varies. The 90° angle produces the highest strain, followed by the 100° angle, then the 110° angle, and subsequently the 120° angle, while the 130° angle results in the lowest strain. These observations indicate that smaller channel angles promote greater plastic deformation.

4.3 Influence of the Friction Coefficient (μ):

The friction coefficient (μ) represents the resistance to sliding between two surfaces in contact when a force is applied. An increase in the friction coefficient can lead to greater resistance to sliding between the workpiece and the contact surfaces, which may alter the distribution of stresses and strains. To study the effect of the friction coefficient (μ), a finite element analysis was conducted to determine the distribution and inhomogeneity of equivalent plastic strains (PEEQ), as well as the evolution of PEEQ at a point on the workpiece during a single pass, using the ABAQUS CAE software. The distribution of equivalent plastic strains for different friction coefficients is shown in Figure 7. A gradual increase in the friction coefficient was applied to study its impact. In the first case, a friction coefficient of $\mu = 0$ was considered, followed by $\mu = 0.0001$ in the second case, and finally $\mu = 0.08$ in the third case. This variation allows for the evaluation of the influence of this parameter on the ECAP (Equal Channel Angular Pressing) process.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 7. Distribution of Equivalent Plastic Strain (PEEQ)

Figure 7 shows the distribution of equivalent plastic strain (PEEQ) as it varies depending on the friction coefficient. It is observed that a higher coefficient leads to greater strains. If the friction coefficient increases further, some elements in this region will be heavily deformed, resulting in an interrupted simulation. In our study, the maximum friction coefficient is set to 0.08 in the simulation. It is also noted that the equivalent plastic strains are much more uniform and significant in the middle region compared to those in the top and bottom regions of the workpiece .

4.4 Evolution of Equivalent Plastic Strain:

To path the evolution of strain during our process, a specific mesh element of the workpiece was selected for continuous monitoring throughout our simulation. The equivalent plastic strain values are provided for time intervals ranging from 0 to 0.5 seconds.

Figure 8. Diagram of the evolution of PEEQ during the ECAP process for the 3 friction cases

Figure 8 illustrates the evolution of equivalent plastic strain (PEEQ) over time for three distinct cases: a first case without friction ($\mu = 0$) and two other cases with different friction coefficients ($\mu = 0.0001$ and $\mu = 0.08$). In the frictionless case ($\mu = 0$), the equivalent plastic strain reaches a value of 0.855 at the end of the simulation. With a friction coefficient of 0.0001, the strain reaches 1.0838, while with a friction coefficient of 0.08, it reaches 1.557. The results show that the friction coefficient of 0.08 leads to the highest strain, closely followed

by 0.0001, while the frictionless case results in the lowest strain. This confirms that a higher friction coefficient leads to greater deformation. After analyzing the impact of different friction coefficients on the distribution of plastic strain, it was determined that the optimal friction coefficient should be chosen based on a balance between strain uniformity and a high strain value. In this regard, a friction coefficient of 0.08 represents an ideal compromise, satisfying both criteria in a balanced manner.

5 VALIDATION OF THE STUDIED MODEL:

5.1 Validation of results concerning the channel angle Φ :

According to the FEM models simulated by reference [13], the authors investigated the influence of the channel angle Φ using the ECAP process on aluminum to study the resulting microstructure after pressing with ECAP. The experiments were conducted using dies with channel angles ranging from 90° to 157.5° . The results show that an ultrafine grain microstructure is only achieved when a very intense plastic strain is imposed on the workpiece during each pass through the die, as in the case of using a die with a channel angle Φ close to 90° . In our study, the results obtained from pressing AISI 1045 steel using ECAP show that the results are comparable to those of reference [13], meaning that a die with a smaller channel angle Φ yields better results. In our case, $\Phi = 90^\circ$.

5.2 Validation of results concerning the friction coefficient μ :

According to the FEM model simulated by [2] using a die with an inner corner angle $\Phi = 120^\circ$ and an outer corner angle $\psi = 20^\circ$, with friction coefficients ranging from 0 to 0.15 during the ECAP of copper, it was shown that as the friction coefficient increases, the average plastic strains also increase. In our study, the results obtained from pressing AISI 1045 steel using ECAP show that as the friction coefficient increases, the equivalent plastic strain

also increases. The 3D FE simulation results demonstrate strong agreement with the findings from references [2] and [13]. This confirms that the proposed 3D finite element model effectively captures the deformation distribution during the ECAP process.

6 CONCLUSION

Equal Channel Angular Pressing (ECAP) is a major severe plastic deformation technique. It involves passing a metallic sample through a bent channel where it undergoes significant deformation while maintaining a constant cross-section. This study has demonstrated that applying ECAP to steel shows significant potential for improving its mechanical properties and ultrafine-grained microstructure. To simulate the ECAP technique and analyze the influence of the channel angle Φ of the die and the friction coefficient μ using a 3D finite element analysis with the ABAQUS software, we modeled and simulated dies with different channel angles ($90^\circ, 100^\circ, 110^\circ, 120^\circ$ and 130°) and different friction coefficients (frictionless, 0.0001 and 0.08). For each case study, we determined the distribution of equivalent plastic strains (PEEQ) and the evolution of plastic strain of an element along the channel.

We determined the optimal values for each parameter:

1. The results indicate that smaller channel angles promote greater plastic deformation. The optimal channel angle was identified as 90° . Further reduction of the channel angle could potentially enhance plastic deformation, which may lead to improvements in certain mechanical properties of the steel.
2. The choice of the friction coefficient directly affects the distribution of strains and can significantly influence the mechanical behavior of the workpiece. A higher friction coefficient results in greater deformations. In this study, the optimal friction coefficient was determined to be 0.08.
3. We also observed that the equivalent plastic strains are significantly more uniform and pronounced in the middle region of the workpiece compared to the top and bottom regions, particularly when using the smaller channel angle and the highest friction coefficient considered.
4. Additionally, the results obtained in our study align with findings previously documented in the literature. This consistency reinforces the validity and coherence of our results, further validating the effectiveness of ECAP in optimizing high-performance materials such as steel. This research underscores the significance of a simulation-based

approach to refining and enhancing material manufacturing processes, paving the way for new advancements in the materials industry.

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